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Ballotion: Bay Leaf Lotion Combination From Bay Leaf Extract and VCO as an Antiseptic Body Lotion to Substitute Hand Sanitizer

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Abstrak

Content of free radicals in the body has a harmful effect, especially on the skin. The skin itself is an organ that will be greatly affected by the presence of free radicals. The structure of the human skin itself is influenced by external and internal factors including: dry air, low air humidity, sunlight, age, various skin diseases and diseases in the body. Free radicals are very reactive molecules because they have unpaired electrons in their outer orbitals so that they are small and can significantly inhibit or prevent oxidation from reacting with body cell molecules by binding to the electrons of these cell molecules. Basically free radicals or bacteria (microorganisms) can be prevented by utilizing the content in plants. Bay leaves were chosen as the main ingredient of this hand sanitizer lotion because this bay plant has antibacterial activity. In accordance with the results of phytochemical screening, bay leaves contain secondary metabolites, namely alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, saponins and steroids. The secondary metabolite compounds are antibacterial so that bacteria attached to the hands can be killed properly, and free radicals in the form of bacteria cannot enter the human body. In the implementing stage, 10 respondents were given bay leaf antiseptic lotion, which was used from 7 August 2021 to 10 August 2021. An antiseptic lotion with a size of 25 grams of lotion per respondent was given. On August 10, 2021, 10 respondents were re-examined after using this Ballotion product. based on the results of interviews conducted, with an open questionnaire method face to face. The durability of this ballotion product is in the range of 5-8 hours, it shows that the aromatic content and activity of antioxidant compounds in the antiseptic lotion of bay leaf extract have great potential if further developed.

Keyword: Bay, VCO, Sanitizer, Bacteria

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INTRODUCTION

Entering the millennial era, people's lifestyle patterns or lifestyles turn to unhealthy modern lifestyles. The increase in population is also accompanied by an increase in the number of existing vehicles where this makes air pollution which causes the number of free radicals in the human body to increase. The content of free radicals in the body has a harmful effect, especially on the skin. The skin itself is an organ that will be greatly affected by the presence of free radicals. The structure of the human skin itself is influenced by external and internal factors including: dry air, low air humidity, sunlight, age, various skin diseases and diseases in the body. These factors can cause excessive evaporation of the skin layer, which results in reduced moisture content in the skin which can cause dry skin. According to (Wasitaatmadja, 1997) skin can naturally form protection, but under certain conditions this cannot be done so that additional non-natural protection is needed. Damage to the skin will cause quite complex health problems to occur.

According to Masyuhara (2009), the process of skin damage is characterized by the appearance of wrinkles, scales, dryness, and cracking caused by free radicals. The skin becomes one of the body's tissues directly that shows the aging process (Cunningham, 2003; in Jusuf, 2012). Based on a survey conducted by the independent research agency Taylor Nelson Sofres (TNS) to 1,800 women aged between 20 – 39 years in five Asian countries: India, Indonesia, Korea, the Philippines and Thailand. The results showed that Asian women began to see signs of aging at an average age of 25 years and 7 months. Seeing the results of the survey, skin care is needed to prevent the skin from becoming dry, rough, and dull. The use of moisturizer in the form of body lotion is one way to overcome this problem. Antioxidant compounds are one of the compounds contained in the lotion. Antioxidant compound is a substance which at substrate concentration is caused by free radicals (Isnindar, et al, 2011). Free radicals are very reactive molecules because they have unpaired electrons in their outer orbitals so that they are small and can significantly inhibit or prevent oxidation from reacting with body cell molecules by binding to the electrons of these cell molecules (Utomo, et al, 2008). Basically the human body itself is able to produce antioxidant compounds, but in small doses so that it will not be able to fight the free radicals produced by the body itself every day. Lack of antioxidants in the body can be overcome through intake from outside which contains lots of antioxidants (Hernani and Rahardjo). , 2005). Natural antioxidants can be produced from vegetables, fruit, herbal plants, and spices, herbal plants, vegetables and fruit. According to Herman & Rahardjo (2005), medicinal herbs have higher antioxidant activity than fruits and vegetables.

Herbal plants that contain antioxidants are very many, one of which is a bay plant. Salam plants or plants that have a Latin name (*Syzygium polyanthum*) are herbal plants in Indonesia which are usually used as cooking spices, the part of this plant that is usually used is the leaves. Bay leaves are widely used by the public to lower cholesterol, diabetes, hypertension, gastritis, and diarrhea. Based on research, bay leaves are known to contain many compounds including flavonoids, selenium, vitamin A, and vitamin E which function as antioxidants (Riansari, 2008). Based on research results, bay leaves contain essential oils, alkaloid compounds, saponins, hydroquinones, triterpenoids, flavonoids and tannins that function as antioxidants (Ekawati 2007; Wijayakusumah et al. 1996; Dalimartha 2000). The results of the flavonoid group test are also in accordance with the research of Pratt (1992), which states that the flavonoid group compounds that have antioxidant activity include flavones, flavonols, isoflavones, catechins, flavonols and chalcones.

Based on research by Amic (2000), it is stated that the antioxidant activity of flavonoids functions as a free radical scavenger associated with the molecular structure and the ortho and para substitution forms of the hydroxyl group. These data are related to the research of Meenakshi et al. (2009) which states that there is a relationship between total flavonoids and antioxidant activity. This study also states that if an ingredient has a high concentration of flavonoid compounds, the higher its antioxidant activity will be. Based on the results of the study, it can be concluded that bay leaf is an herbal plant that has many benefits that can be used to protect the skin from free radicals, but the use of bay leaves directly without being processed and used directly on the skin is impractical and cannot be utilized optimally. Seeing this, the solution, bay leaves will be made into a topical dosage form by extracting bay leaves and then formulated into a lotion dosage form. Based on the content contained in the bay leaf, it can be made into a pharmaceutical preparation by formulating it into a topical dosage form, one of which is lotion.

Lotion itself includes preparations in the form of emulsions or suspensions which are usually used for topical use. The use of lotion is recommended and suitable for use in the general public because it can cover a wider area of skin and dry quickly on the skin

after use (Ansel, 1989). The use of lotion was chosen by the community because it is easier to use on the skin because of its consistency that is not too dense which makes the lotion content spread more evenly on a large surface of the skin, and dries quickly after use so it is practical and efficient when used. The lotion innovation from bay leaf extract will have a dual function as an antiseptic lotion to replace hand sanitizer. Bay leaf extract which has very strong antioxidant activity is expected to have a high SPF value so that it can protect the skin from the sun.

The year 2020 will be a tough year for countries around the world, where the corona virus has spread throughout the country. Coronavirus is a new type of virus that can cause symptoms such as MERS-CoV and SARS-CoV. The transmission of this corona virus also spread very quickly, resulting in the World Health Organization (WHO) establishing the virus as a national disaster that threatens a public health emergency. The government has made various efforts to break the chain of the spread of the COVID-19 virus, one of which is the use of implementing a health protocol, namely the use of masks, social distancing and washing hands. Washing hands is one of the mandatory health protocols that must be implemented in the community, but sometimes there are places that do not allow people to wash their hands with running water. Seeing this problem, people can wash their hands using hand sanitizer, this is considered a practical and effective step. The content of the hand sanitizer itself from several existing products can even kill 99% of existing germs which is very practical in supporting the implementation of health protocols during this pandemic.

The demand for hand sanitizer products during this pandemic has even increased rapidly, seeing this phenomenon, manufacturers are competing to produce hand sanitizer products, so there are some manufacturers who deliberately use hazardous chemicals just to meet product demand. Some hand sanitizer products contain a lot of alcohol where the ingredients can cause irritation to the skin. This is because the alcohol content is flammable so that it causes side effects that are quite dangerous for the user if used for a long time. This phenomenon also makes the innovation of making hand sanitizers made from non-alcoholic an alternative for people who have high sensitivity to alcohol content. Seeing this problem, an antiseptic lotion made from bay leaf was created as a substitute for hand sanitizer. The use of hand sanitizer can reduce the risk of dry skin due to washing hands too often with soap and can cause irritation if used repeatedly. The content of bay leaves is also effective in killing germs naturally without chemicals.

Bay leaves were chosen as the main ingredient of this hand sanitizer lotion because this bay plant has antibacterial activity. Salam plants have the highest chemical content in the leaves. Bay leaves have a chelating taste and are astringent. Chemical compounds contained in bay leaves are flavonoids, tannins, essential oils, triterpenoids, alkaloids, and steroids. This content can inhibit the growth of *Streptococcus* spp bacteria. found throughout the body. Flavonoids, tannins, essential oils, and alkaloids have antibacterial effects while triterpenoid steroids and steroids have analgesic effects. These activities make bay leaf oil suitable as an alternative natural ingredient to replace alcohol which is suitable for use in hand sanitizer gel lotion formulations (Menganti, 2017).

In the study (Tammi, 2016) showed that bay leaf extract produced the most effective inhibition zone for *Staphylococcus aureus* at a concentration of 60% (20 mm) and for *Escherichia coli*, it was not yet effective because there was no inhibition found at each level. Hand sanitizers are generally formulated in the form of a gel lotion that provides a soft and comfortable sensation to use on the skin. The contents of the gel lotion include a gelling agent that plays a role in making consistency, humectants that play a role in attracting water and have the ability to hydrate the stratum corneum layer. Therefore, this hand sanitizer made from bay leaf extract is a lotion that is relatively safe to use. An

antiseptic lotion that can moisturize the skin and kill germs at the same time.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The design method chosen in this study is a systematic review. A systematic review is included in secondary studies which is a research method to identify, evaluate and interpret the results of previous studies that are relevant to the question, topic, or phenomenon that is the focus of attention. The literature used will pass through 4 stages, namely: identification, screening, eligibility, and inclusion. The following are the stages carried out in a systematic review in this study, Building questions Scoping search, Device protocol, Comprehensive search related to the topic discussed, Choose a study based on the eligibility criteria, Assess studies using quality checklists, Extracting existing data, Perform analysis of results, Interpret findings, Disseminate reports, and the method for making this product we need to prepare:

1. Virgin coconut oil (VCO)
2. Bay leaf extract
3. Beeswax
4. Glycerin.

The methods of making this product is:

1. First of all we need to prepare all the materials.
2. Then, melt 100 gram of beeswax.
3. Mix 100 gram of beeswax with 175 ml VCO.
4. Then, we need to extract 15 bay leaves by blend it with 400 ml of water.
5. Filter it and mix all the materials.
6. Last, we need to test to respondent with a sample respondent test. This test to see product durability indicator and anti-irritant.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Based on the results of the clear zone test, the inhibition of bay leaf extract (*S. Polyanthum*) against *Pityosporum ovale* was carried out by suspending 0.1 ml of *P. ovale* in each cup containing PDA media using a sterile swab method which was then dripped with ethyl compounds from the leaf extract. regards. This indicates that there is a clear zone formed due to the administration of ethyl acetate compound bay leaf extract. This is due to the activity of secondary metabolites such as alkaloids, flavonoids which can damage the membranes and cell walls of *P. ovale* bacteria, or this is commonly known as the antifungal effect (Nasution, Sri, LR. et al :2021). Based on this study, the high antioxidant content of bay leaf extract can inhibit the growth of the fungus *Pityosporum ovale*, it can be concluded that bay leaf extract has the potential as an antibacterial and fungal ingredient.

Pictures 1. *Pityosporum ovale*

Basically, to determine the content of active compounds in bay leaf extract (*Syzygiumpolyanthum*), a phytochemical screening test was carried out. The results of the phytochemical screening test for bay leaf extract (*Syzygiumpolyanthum*) are as follows.

Table 1. Phytochemical screening results

Active Compound	Bay Leaf Extract
Alkaloids	+
Flavonoids	+
Tanins	+
Saponins	+
Triterpenods	-
Steroids	+

According to Evendi (2017), the results of the phytochemical screening test showed that bay leaf extract (*Syzygiumpolyanthum*) contains alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, saponins and steroids. Alkaloids are active compounds of secondary metabolites that can be found in nature, it is because these compounds are produced by plants. Alkaloids belong to the largest class of secondary plant substances, alkaloids include basic compounds containing one or more nitrogen atoms, usually in combination as part of a cyclic system. The structure of this type of alkaloid is known to have a basic wavelength of 535 nm and a molecular weight of 389 g/mol. Alkaloids have anti-bacterial activity, with the mechanism of inhibiting esterase, DNA and RNA polymerase, also inhibiting cellular respiration and playing a role in DNA intercalation.

Pictures 2. Alkaloid Compounds

Flavonoids are the largest group of phenolic compounds found in nature. These compounds are red, purple, blue, and some yellow dyes found in plants. Structurally, flavonoids consist of two benzene rings linked through a heterocyclic ring. These compounds have many biochemical benefits, but almost all types of flavonoids are useful as natural antioxidants. The function of flavonoids in plants in general acts as a regulator of plant growth and a regulator of photosynthetic activity. In addition to acting as a regulator of growth and photosynthesis, this active compound acts as an anti-bacterial, with a mechanism for degrading bacteria on the surface and inside of the human body.

Pictures 3. Flavonoid Compounds

Tannins are a type of phenolic which acts as an antibacterial. Tannins are soluble in polar organic solvents to a certain extent, but are insoluble in non-polar organics. Tannins are active compounds that are able to withstand attacks from outside the plant body such as termites, so this compound can also be used as an anti-termite. Besides being useful as an anti-termite, this active compound can be used as an anti-bacterial for the human body. There are even several types of tannins that act as antioxidants and can inhibit enzymes such as reverse transcriptase and DNA topoisomerase.

Pictures 4. Tanins Compounds

Saponins are a class of natural compounds that are very potential. Saponin compounds have polar and non-polar groups that are surface active so that when saponins are shaken with water they will undergo hydrolysis and can form micelles. Saponins belong to the class of terpenoid compounds and are part of the triterpenoids derived from hydrocarbons (C₃₀). This compound is soap-like and can be detected by the ability to form a lot of foam when extracting plants or concentration of plant extracts that can repair cells. Saponins are active compounds of secondary metabolites which have anti-bacterial benefits for humans. Structurally, the nature of this saponin as a base, so that saponins can be applied in the form of soap or body lotion.

Pictures 5. Saponin Compounds

Steroids are a class of secondary metabolites. These groups of compounds are known to have bioinsecticide, antibacterial, antifungal and antidiabetic activities that can be produced by bay leaves. Viewed as an antibacterial, the content of this compound can kill one type of bacteria such as *Staphylococcus aureus* (Hidayah et al, 2016).

Pictures 6. Steroid Compounds

In addition, this research is strengthened by research conducted by Debnath et.al: 2007 which states that the content of alkaloid compounds in bay leaf extract is able to suppress and inhibit esterase, DNA, polymerase, RNA, and can inhibit cell respiration. Ballotion: Bay leave lotion from bay leaf extract and co as an antiseptic body lotion to substitute hand sanitizer were tested on 10 respondents with different age categories, different professions. This research was conducted in Karangpring Village, Sukorambi Jember. On August 5, 2021, a product sample production process was carried out in the form of an antiseptic lotion from inner leaves. The sample product was then tested on 10 respondents in this village. Sample testing was carried out in three important stages, namely testing, implementing, and evaluating.

At the testing stage, the sample product will be tested on the respondent's hand area, with the aim of seeing the side effects of using this lotion. based on research conducted using Ballotion proved to not cause irritation, and allergies in all respondents (Figure 1 and 2)

Figure 1. Testing one of the respondents (Dhani)

Figure 2. Results after 30 minutes of use

Pictures 7. Testing one of the respondents

In the implementing stage, 10 respondents were given bay leaf antiseptic lotion, which was used from 7 August 2021 to 10 August 2021. An antiseptic lotion with a size of 25 grams of lotion per respondent was given. On August 10, 2021, 10 respondents were re-examined after using this Ballotion product. based on the results of interviews conducted, with an open questionnaire method face to face. It was found that the use of this ballotion product did not have dangerous side effects such as irritation, itching, rash or others, besides that people quite liked the aroma of this bay leaf extract antiseptic lotion, respondents said that the aroma of this bay leaf extract provided an aromatherapy effect. soothing and not stinging.

The last test was carried out on August 11, 2021, to test the durability of the product in a simple way, during the process of giving the product to our respondents we provide information about the durability of this product, where for each product use the respondent must count how many hours regarding the durability of this ballotion, this test we use an aromatic indicator on the product, where when the product is felt to have been lost, the respondent will record it which is then packaged in the following statistical data.

Pictures 7. Statistical Data

Based on the statistical data above, it shows that the durability of this ballotion product is in the range of 5-8 hours. Based on a simple product resistance test, an average yield of 6.27 hours can be taken, it shows that the aromatic content and activity of antioxidant compounds in the antiseptic lotion of bay leaf extract have great potential if further developed.

CONCLUSION

Bay leaf extract has the potential as an antibacterial which is caused by activity of secondary metabolites such as alkaloids, flavonoids. Bay leaf extract (*Syzygium polyanthum*) contains alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, saponins and steroids. Ballotion: Bay leave lotion from bay leaf extract and co as an antiseptic body lotion to substitute hand sanitizer were tested on 10 respondents with different age categories, different professions. The result of this ballotion product did not have dangerous side effects such as irritation, itching, rash or others, besides that people quite liked the aroma of this bay leaf extract antiseptic lotion, respondents said that the aroma of this bay leaf extract provided an aromatherapy effect. The durability of this ballotion product is in the range of 5-8 hours, it shows that the aromatic content and activity of antioxidant compounds in the antiseptic lotion of bay leaf extract have great potential if further developed.

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